

SONLAR NAZARIYSI USULLARI YORDAMIDA KO'P O'LCHOVLI FREDGOLM 2-TUR INTEGRAL TENGLAMASINI TAQRIBIY YECHISH

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ko'rib chiqilayotgan Fredgolm 2-tur integral tenglamalarni taqribiy yechish usuli, iteratsiya usuli bilan optimal koeffitsiyentlar usulini birlashtirib, quyidagi Fredgolm 2-tur integral tenglamalarining yechimlarini qarab chiqamiz

Kalit so'zlar: Fredgolm 2-tur integral tenglamalar, kvadratur formulalar, integrallarni taqribiy yechishning son-nazariy usuli.

Keyinchalik qulaylik uchun quyidagicha belgilashlar kiritamiz:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \bar{a} &= (a_1, \dots, a_n), & \bar{l} &= (l_1, \dots, l_n), & \bar{m} &= (m_1, \dots, m_n), \\ \bar{t} &= (t_1, \dots, t_n), & \bar{dt} &= (dt_1, \dots, dt_n), & \bar{p} &= (x_1, \dots, x_s), \\ (\bar{a}, \bar{m}) &= a_1 m_1 + \dots + a_n m_n, & K(\bar{m}) &= \prod_{i=1}^n \max(1, |m_i|), \\ M_{kn} &= \left(\left\{ \frac{am}{N} \right\} \right), & Q_j &= (y_{(j-1)s+1}, \dots, y_{js}), j = 1, 2, \dots, n, \\ \bar{Q} &= (Q_1, \dots, Q_n), dQ = dy_1 dy_2 \dots dy_{sn} = dQ_1 dQ_2 \dots dQ_n, \\ \Phi_n(x, \bar{t}) &= \sum_{j_1, \dots, j_n}^q K_{ij_1}(x, t_1) \prod_{v=2}^n K_{j_{v-1}j_v}(t_{v-1}, t_v) f_{j_n}(t_n) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1)$$

Iteratsiya usuli bilan optimal koeffitsiyentlar usulini birlashtirib, quyidagi Fredgolm 2-tur integral tenglamalarining yechimlarini qarab chiqamiz

$$y(P) = f(P) + \gamma \int_0^1 \dots \int_0^1 K(P, Q) y(Q) dQ \quad (2)$$

(2) tenglamada ozod had va yadroni quyidagi shart qanoatlantirsin:

$$f(P) \in E_n^\alpha(C_1) \quad K(P, Q) \in E_{2n}^\alpha(C_2) \quad (3)$$

(2) tenglama yechimini Neyman qatori ko'rinishida izlaymiz

$$y(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \lambda^n \varphi_n(x) \quad (4)$$

Bu yerda λ - kichik parametr bo'lib, $\varphi_j(x)$ funksiyasi esa aniqlanishi kerak.

(4) ni (2) ga qo'yib, integrallash va umumlashtirishni o'rniga qo'yib (bunday almashtirishning qonuniyligini ko'rsatish qiyin emas), ega bo'lamizki

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \lambda^n \varphi_j(x) = f(x) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{j=1}^q \lambda^n \int_0^1 K_j(x, t) \varphi_{n-1}(x) dx \quad (5)$$

Teng kuchli λ larda koeffitsiyentlarni tenglashtirib, ba'zi o'zgartirishlar dan so'ng, ega bo'lamiz

$$\varphi_0(x) = f(x),$$

$$\varphi_n(x) = \int_0^1 \dots \int_0^1 \sum_{j_1, \dots, j_n}^q K_{j_1}(x, t_1) \prod_{l=2}^n K_{j_{l-1}j_l}(t_{l-1}t_l) \times \\ \times f_{j_n}(t_n) dt_1 \dots dt_n \quad (6)$$

Yoki (3.1) dan $\varphi_n(x) = \int_{G_n} \Phi_n(x, t) dt$, bu yerda G_n - birlik n o'lchovli kub.

Lemmadan foydalanib, $\Phi_n(x, t)$ funksiya t_1, \dots, t_n larda $E_n^\alpha(q^n A^n C_2^n C_1)$ sinfiga tegishli, x, t_1, \dots, t_n funksiyada esa $E_{n+1}^\alpha(q^n A^{n+1} C_2^{n+1} C_1)$ sinfiga tegishli deb atashimiz mumkin, bu yerda

$$A = 2^{\alpha+1} \left(3 + \frac{2}{\alpha-1} \right)$$

N - o'suvchi natural son bo'lsin va $|\lambda| < \left(\frac{3\alpha q A^2 C_2}{2(\alpha-1)} \right)^{-1}$

ga ega bo'lamiz. 8-lemmadan foydalanib, $\Phi_n(x, t)$ t_1, \dots, t_n funksiya sifatida $E_{n+1}^\alpha(q^n A^n C_2^n C_1)$ sinfiga tegishli, x, t_1, \dots, t_n funksiya sifatida $E_{n+1}^\alpha(q^n A^{n+1} C_2^{n+1} C_1)$ sinfiga tegishli funksiya ekanligini ko'rsatish mumkin, bu yerda

$$A = 2^{\alpha+1} \left(3 + \frac{2}{\alpha-1} \right)$$

N - o'suvchi natural son bo'lsin va $|\lambda| < \left(\frac{3\alpha q A^2 C_2}{2(\alpha-1)} \right)^{-1}$

N_1 va M natural sonlarini quyidagicha aniqlaymiz

$$N_1 = \left[N^{\frac{1}{2}} \log \frac{-\beta}{2} N \right], \quad M = \left[\frac{(\alpha-1) \log N - (\alpha\beta - \beta + 2) \log \log N}{2(\log \log N - \log(|\lambda| q A^2 C_2))} \right]. \quad (7)$$

Quyidagi teorema o'rinli.

Teorema. $N \geq 2^\alpha$ da, $\alpha > 1$ bo'lsin, (2.2) sharti bajarilsin. U holda (2.1) sistemaning yechimi uchun quyidagi tenglik o'rinli

$$y_i(x) = f_i(x) + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^M \lambda^n \sum_{k=1}^N \Phi_{in}(x, M_{kn}) + R_N, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, q, \quad (8)$$

bu yerda

$$R_N = O \left(D N^{-\frac{\alpha-1}{2}} \log^{0.5(\alpha-1)\beta + M - 1} N \right), \quad |0| < 1,$$

$D = D(\alpha, \lambda, q, A, C_1, C_2) - N$ ga bog'liq bo'lmagan doimiy

Isbot. V.S.Ryabenkoga ko‘ra [53], quyidagi tenglik yordamida trigonometrik polinom $P_{inN_1}(x,t)$ ni aniqlaymiz

$$\hat{C}_i(x, m) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \Phi_{in}(x, M_{kn}) e^{-2\pi i \frac{(m,a)k}{N}}, \quad (9)$$

$$P_{inN_1}(x, t) = \sum_{k(m) < N_1} \hat{C}_i(x, m) e^{2\pi i(m,t)} \quad (10)$$

(2.9) ni (2.10) ga olib borib qo'yib,

$$P_{inN_1}(x, t) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \Phi_{in}(x, M_{kn}) \psi_{kn}(t), \quad (11)$$

hosil qilamiz.

Bu yerda

$$\psi_{kn}(t) = \sum_{k(m) < N_1} e^{2\pi i(m, t - \frac{\alpha k}{N})} \quad (12)$$

Endi $\Phi_{in}(x,t)$ funksiya ko‘rinishini quyidagicha yozamiz

$$\Phi_{in} \Phi_{in}(x,t) = P_{knN_1}(x,t) + r_{inN_1}(x,t). \quad (13)$$

(2) tengligini quyidagi ko‘rinishda yozib olamiz

$$y_i(x) = f_i(x) + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \sum_{n=1}^M \lambda^n g_{knN_1} \Phi_{in}(x, M_{kn}) + \sum_{n=1}^M \lambda^n R_{inN_1}(x) + \sum_{n=M+1}^{\infty} \lambda^n \varphi_{in}(x), \quad (14)$$

bu yerda

$$R_{inN_1}(x) = \int_{G_n} r_{inN_1}(x, t) dt, \quad (15)$$

va

$$\begin{aligned} \acute{g}_{knN_1} &= \int_{G_n} \psi_{knN_1}(t) dt = \sum_{k(m) < N_1} \int_{G_n} e^{2\pi i(m, t - \frac{\alpha k}{N})} dt = \\ &= \sum_{k(m) < N_1} e^{2\pi i(m, \frac{\alpha k}{N})} \int_{G_n} e^{2\pi i(m, t)} dt = 1. \end{aligned}$$

Endi (14) dagi oxirgi ikkita yig‘indi (summa) bilan shug‘ullanamiz.

$C_{ir}(x,m)$ va $C_{i\phi}(x,m)$ koeffitsiyentlari orqali Furye funksiyalarini mos ravishda $r_{inN_1}(x,t)$

va $\Phi_{in}(x,t)$ deb belgilaymiz. U holda

$$r_{inN_1}(x, t) = \sum_m C_{ir}(x, m) e^{2\pi i(m,t)} \quad (16)$$

$$\Phi_{in}(x, t) = \sum_m C_{i\phi}(x, m) e^{2\pi i(m,t)} \quad (17)$$

Bu yerda \sum_m n -o‘lchovli fazoning barcha nuqtalari uchun yig‘indini ifodalaydi .(10) va (13) tengliklaridan

$$C_{ir}(x,m) = \begin{cases} c_{i\Phi}(x, m) - c_1(x, m), & \text{если } K(m) < N_1 \\ C_{i\Phi}(x, m), & \text{если } K(m) \geq N_1 \end{cases}$$

tenglikka ega bo‘lamiz .

$$|R_{inN_1}(x)| \leq \sum_{K(m) < N_1} |C_{i\Phi}(x, m) - C_1(x, m)| + \sum_{K(m) \geq N_1} |C_{i\Phi}(x, m)|. \quad (18)$$

Birinchi yig‘indining bahosi uchun 8-lemmani o‘zgartiramiz. Lekin bu holda n – o‘zgaruvchi kattalik , shuning uchun ushbu lemmada ishtirok etuvchi C_0, C_1 va $C=C_0^\alpha + nB^n$ o‘zgarishlarining n gq aloqasini aniqlash kerak , bu yerda

$B < 3 + \frac{2}{\alpha-1}$. Optimal koeffitsiyentlar ta‘rifi va 2- lemmaga ko‘ra , quyidagilardan ega bo‘lamiz

$$C_0 < 2 \left(2 + \frac{3}{\log N} \right)^n$$

$$\Phi_{in}(x, t) \in En_n^\alpha(q^n A^n C_2^n C_1). \quad (19)$$

U holda

$$C = C_1(qAC_2)^n$$

Endi, 9-lemmani $\Phi_{in}(x,t)e^{-2\pi i(m,t)}$ funksiyasiga almashtirib , quyidagini hosil qilamiz

$$\begin{aligned} & |C_{i\Phi}(x, m) - C_i(x, m)| = \\ & = \left| \int_{G_n} \Phi_{in}(x, t) e^{-2\pi i(m,t)} dt - \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \Phi_{in}(x, M_{kn}) e^{-\frac{2\pi ik}{N}} \right| \leq \\ & \leq C_1(qAC_1)^n AN_1^\alpha N^{-\alpha} (C_0^\alpha + nB^n) \log^{\alpha\beta} N_1. \end{aligned}$$

Ko‘rinib turibdiki har bir $N \geq 2^\alpha$

$$C_0^\alpha + nB^n < A^n \left[\frac{n}{2^{n(\alpha+1)}} + \frac{\left(2 + \frac{3}{\log N} \right)^{\alpha n}}{2^{\alpha n} \left(3 + \frac{2}{\alpha + 1} \right)^n} \right] < A^n.$$

Shuning uchun

$$|C_{i\Phi}(x, m) - C_i(x, m)| \leq C_i A (qA^2 C_2)^n N_1^\alpha N^{-\alpha} \log^{\alpha\beta} N_1.$$

Bundan esa,

$$|R_{inN_1}(x)| \leq C_1(qAC_2)^n \left(A^{n+1} N_1^{\alpha+1} N^{-\alpha} \log^{\alpha\beta+n-1} N_1 + \alpha \left(\frac{\alpha}{\alpha-1} \right)^n N_1^{-\alpha+1} \log^{n-1} N_1 \right)$$

Bundan N_1 ning tarifini eslab, ba’zi almashtirishdan keyin, quyidagiga ega bo‘lamiz

$$\left| \sum_{n=1}^M \lambda^n R_{inN_1}(x) \right| \leq C_1 N^{-\frac{\alpha}{2} + \frac{1}{2}} \log^{0,5(\alpha-1)\beta + M-1} N \left[\frac{2A}{2^{\alpha\beta}} \sum_{n=1}^M \left(\frac{3|\lambda|qA^2 C_2}{2} \right)^n + \right.$$

$$+2\alpha \sum_{n=1}^M \left(\frac{3|\lambda|qA^2C_2}{2(\alpha-1)} \right)^n \leq 3|\lambda|qA^2C_1C_2 \left[\frac{2\alpha^2}{2(\alpha-1) - 3|\lambda|qA^2C_2} + \frac{2^{1-\alpha\beta}A}{2 - 3|\lambda|qA^2C_2} \right] N^{-\frac{\alpha-1}{2}} g^{0,5(\alpha-1)\beta+M-1} N. \quad (20)$$

(19) ni hisobga olib (18) dagi so'nggi qatorni baholaymiz

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \sum_{n=M+1}^{\infty} \lambda^n \varphi_{in}(x) \right| &= \left| \sum_{n=M+1}^{\infty} \lambda^n \int_{G_n} \sum_{n=M+1}^{\infty} \lambda^n \varphi_{in}(x, t) dt \right| \leq \\ &\leq \sum_{n=M+1}^{\infty} |\lambda|^n \sum_m \frac{(qAC_2)^n C_1}{K(m)^\alpha} \leq C_1 \sum_{n=M+1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^\alpha} (|\lambda|qA^2C_2)^n = \\ &= C_1 \frac{(|\lambda|qA^2C_2)^{M+1}}{2^\alpha(1 - |\lambda|qA^2C_2)}. \quad (21) \end{aligned}$$

(20) - (21) baholarni birlashtirgan va M ning ma'nosini eslagan holda, ega bo'lamiz

$$y_i(x) = f_i(x) + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^M \lambda^n \sum_{k=1}^N \Phi_{in}(x, M_{kn}) + R_N,$$

Bunda

$$R_N = \theta DN^{-\frac{\alpha-1}{2}} \log^{0,5(\alpha-1)\beta+M-1} N, \quad |\theta| < 1$$

$$D = |\lambda|qA^2C_1C_2 \left[\frac{6\alpha^2}{2(\alpha-1) - 3\alpha|\lambda|qA^2C_2} + \frac{6(2^{-\alpha\beta}A)}{2 - 3|\lambda|qA^2C_2} + \frac{1}{1 - |\lambda|qA^2C_2} \right].$$

Shu bilan 1-teorema isbotlandi.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR

1. Коробов Н.М. Теоретикочисловые методы в приближенном анализе. –М.: Физматгиз. 1963. 224 с.
2. Коробов Н.М. О вычислении оптимальных коэффициентов //ДАН СССР. 1982. том 267. №2.
3. Коробов Н.М. Тригонометрические суммы и их приложения. –М.: “Наука”, 1989. 237с.
4. Исраилов М.И., Шадиметов Х.М. Оптимальные коэффициенты Весовых квадратурных формул для сингулярных интегралов типа Коши // ДАН УзССР. 1991. №11. С. 7-9.